

Simulating synthetic missing person databases for investigative purposes

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Abstract

Missing person search is a complex process that involves several steps. From preliminary investigation to DNA kinship test, several lines of evidence are collected during the process. Due to ethical and anonymity aspects, accounting for real databases of missing and unidentified persons is not so common. Nevertheless, having these datasets for investigative purposes is crucial to develop methods and tools for assisting in the search. Here, we fill this gap, providing functions for simulating missing person cases under different scenarios. Our methods are open-source available and integrated into the `mispitools` R package, freely available on CRAN.

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1. Introduction

The search for missing persons is a multifaceted process that involves the collection and analysis of various types of evidence, ranging from initial investigative information to advanced DNA kinship testing [1], [2]. Each stage of the investigation contributes to building a case, ultimately aimed at identifying the missing individual. A critical challenge in advancing the development of methods and tools for missing person investigations lies in the limited availability of real-world datasets [3], [4]. Particularly to address the development of models that relies in integrating different sources of evidence [5]–[7]. Ethical concerns, privacy issues, and the protection of individuals' anonymity make the use of actual missing persons and unidentified remains databases rare. As a result, forensic researchers and developers of investigative tools face significant barriers in testing and refining their methods on realistic datasets, which are crucial for improving search and identification processes [8].

To address this, researchers have explored alternative approaches, including the generation of synthetic datasets [9]. These datasets allow investigators to simulate real-world scenarios in a controlled, ethical manner, enabling them to test the robustness of forensic methods and identify potential areas for improvement. Previous efforts in this field have focused on generating synthetic DNA profiles [10]–[12] or simulating specific aspects of forensic investigations [13]. The utility of these simulations has been proven [14], [15]. It allows to exhaustively evaluate mathematical models and strategies developed to assist the search [16]. Moreover, one of the key applications of computational simulations has been its use for evaluating the statistical power of the DNA-based search, exploring the expected values of the likelihood ratio, a key metric in forensic science [10], [17], [18].

Here present a framework for simulating synthetic missing person databases designed specifically for investigative purposes. This approach allows users to create realistic datasets that mimic the complexities and variability of real missing person cases. These simulations cover a wide range of scenarios, including different family structures, relationships, and genetic profiles, offering a versatile tool for forensic practitioners and researchers. By simulating the entire process of a missing person investigation, from the initial stages of evidence collection to the final kinship test, our methods provide a valuable resource for testing and refining forensic tools in a controlled environment.

The methods we introduce are integrated into the `mispitools` R package [8], an open-source platform designed for forensic genetics and kinship analysis. Available freely on CRAN, `mispitools` offers users a suite of functions that allow them to simulate missing per-

son cases under various parameters. This tool enables researchers to generate datasets tailored to specific investigative scenarios, facilitating the development and evaluation of new methods and software. By providing a flexible, accessible framework, we aim to support the forensic community in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of missing person searches.

2. Methods

Synthetic datasets representing missing person scenarios were generated using the `mispitools` R package [8]. Two primary scenarios were considered: cases involving children and cases involving adult populations. The data generation process involved specifying parameters such as case type, date of disappearance, and various demographic probabilities, including gender proportion and regional representation.

The simulation functions `makePOIprelim()` and `makeMPprelim()` were implemented with the flexibility to simulate a wide range of missing person cases. Each case type was designed with specific attributes that reflect real-world variations. For example, for children's cases, the model included attributes such as birth type, age, and region, whereas for migrants, height and weight distributions, as well as regional data, were considered.

To add realism to the dataset, height and weight were modeled as continuous variables influenced by age and gender. For children, height was modeled as a linear function of age, with height increasing by 5 cm per year on average. The weight of the individuals was modeled similarly, increasing by 2.5 kg per year. For migrants, we took a similar approach, adjusting the means and deviations to reflect adult growth patterns. All simulations were performed using a random number generation process, ensuring both variability and replicability.

Validation of the simulated datasets was performed by generating summary statistics and visualization plots, including histograms, box-plots, and scatter plots. These visualizations allowed us to assess the distribution of attributes such as age, height, and weight across different demographic groups, confirming that the synthetic data matched expected real-world patterns. Furthermore, we performed regression analyses to study relationships between different variables, such as age, height, and weight, which were compared against empirical data from real-world population studies.

The framework also incorporates probabilistic aspects, such as assigning sex and place of birth based on defined probability distributions. For each individual, key demographic and biometric variables were simulated to capture the variability seen in actual populations.

By adjusting the input parameters, diverse scenarios were simulated for testing different investigative approaches and forensic methodologies.

3. Results

The results of the synthetic data generation and subsequent analyses are presented in this section. For adults, weight and height distributions were analyzed across different regions to observe regional variability. The boxplots presented in Figure 1 illustrate the distribution of weight and height for adults in Africa, Asia, Europe, North America, Oceania, and South America. The median weight and height values exhibited variations by region, with some regions, such as Africa, displaying slightly higher medians. The interquartile ranges also provided insight into the variability within each region.

Figure 1. Weight and height distributions by region for adults.

The boxplots show the median, interquartile range, and potential outliers for each region, highlighting the differences in anthropometric characteristics across various geographic areas.

For children, weight and height distributions were similarly analyzed across different regions, as shown in Figure 2. The boxplots indicate that children from different regions exhibit distinct height and weight distributions. The median values for height and weight are comparable across regions, but slight differences exist, which can be attributed to regional factors such as access to healthcare and nutrition. The overall spread of height and weight appears consistent, suggesting that the model adequately captures the expected variability among children.

Figure 2. Weight and height distributions by region for children. The figure highlights regional disparities in growth patterns among children, with differences in median values.

The correlation between height and weight in children was further examined and is depicted in Figure 3. A strong linear relationship was observed, with weight increasing proportionally to height. This relationship was quantified using regression analysis, which indicated a significant positive correlation between height and weight. The results align with expected growth patterns in children, providing validation for the synthetic data's accuracy in representing real-world trends.

Figure 3. Correlation between height and weight in children. The scatter plot demonstrates a strong positive correlation, indicating that as height increases, weight also tends to increase. This relationship is consistent with typical growth patterns observed in children and supports the validity of the simulated dataset. The regression line ($R^2 = 0.91$) provides a visual representation of the trend, emphasizing the linear association between the two variables.

For adults, the correlation between height and weight was found to be less pronounced compared to children. Although not included in the primary figures, additional analyses indicated that the relationship between height and weight in adults showed a weaker linear trend, suggesting a more complex interplay between these variables in the adult population.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed and analyzed synthetic datasets representing missing person scenarios involving both children and adult populations. The synthetic data demonstrated consistent and realistic distributions for key anthropometric variables, including height and weight, across different regions. The visualizations and regression analyses confirmed that the simulated data aligned with expected real-world trends, especially for children, where a strong positive correlation between height and weight was observed.

The regional analyses for both adults and children highlighted the possibility of adding differences in growth patterns, which may be attributed to various socio-economic and environmental factors and affect the general search [19]. While the correlation between height and weight in adults was less pronounced, the dataset still provided valuable insights into the variability and complexity of adult anthropometric characteristics and can be adjusted to have different degrees of correlation.

The utility of the generated datasets lies in their potential application for forensic and investigative research. By simulating realistic missing person cases, we provide a tool that can be used to test and validate new methodologies under controlled conditions. However, it is important to recognize the limitations of synthetic data, particularly in capturing the full scope of real-world variability and complexity.

Future work should focus on further refining the synthetic data generation process by incorporating additional demographic and genetic variables to enhance realism. Additionally, validation against larger empirical datasets would strengthen the reliability of the synthetic datasets and their applicability in forensic investigations.

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